

S1 Table. The intra-observer reliability at detecting social interactions according to the ethogram developed in Foris et al. (2019) in 2 video sequences. The observer coded each video sequence twice (original and repetition).

Video duration	True Positives	False Positives	False Negatives	Sensitivity	Precision
168 min	22	5	2	0.92	0.81
155 min	21	5	1	0.95	0.81
Total: 323 min	43	10	3	0.94	0.81

True Positives (TP): interactions found by the observer at both time points

False Positives (FP): interactions only found by the observer in the repetition

False Negatives (FN): interactions only found by the observer in the original

Sensitivity = $TP / (TP + FN)$

Precision = $TP / (TP + FP)$

Reference

Foris, B., M. Zebunke, J. Langbein, and N. Melzer. 2019. Comprehensive analysis of affiliative and agonistic social networks in lactating dairy cattle groups. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 210:60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2018.10.016>.